

Guidelines : How to manage your emails

Emails as organizational records

In an organizational context, emails span the full range of professional activities and can, in some cases, be considered records.

Within the NGO, emails may contain information of evidentiary value: decisions taken, strategic plans under development, meeting summaries, document exchanges, actions carried out, and more.

Thus, emails can be both a source of evidence and a tool of institutional memory. As such, they are subject to the regulatory and administrative obligations that govern the retention and preservation of records.

A **record** is any information, regardless of format, that is created, received, and maintained by an organization as evidence of a legal obligation or as a trace of administrative activity. This includes letters, reports, invoices, maps, photographs, contracts, and other documents that reflect the policies, decisions, and actions of the NGO and ensure their understanding in the future.

In contrast, some types of information are **not considered records**. These are referred to as non-record materials or items of temporary value. Examples include personal messages, reference documents, newsletters from external organizations, internal announcements with no evidentiary value, and blank forms. These types of content do not reflect decision-making or official actions.

Benefits and risks of good/poor email management

Benefits of good email management

- Ensures quick access to important messages and attachments
- Supports informed decision-making by preserving relevant exchanges
- Improves operational efficiency by reducing clutter and duplication
- Enhances accountability through the traceability of decisions and actions
- Contributes to good governance by preserving policy and procedural records
- Helps identify and protect sensitive or personal data contained in email
- Ensures emails are retained for the appropriate duration, according to legal and business needs
- Preserves the institution's memory, especially during staff transitions

Risks of poor email management

- Risk of poor decisions due to missing or outdated information
- Inability to prove actions, approvals, or decisions when needed
- Loss of time searching for misfiled or inaccessible messages
- Increased storage costs from keeping obsolete or redundant emails
- Exposure to privacy and security breaches if sensitive emails are mishandled
- Difficulty identifying critical communications in emergencies
- Legal exposure if evidence cannot be produced in case of disputes or audits
- Loss of valuable institutional knowledge when staff leave without transferring key messages

How to identify which emails to keep or delete

Adapted from the open program "Digital Records Pathways: Topics in Digital Preservation. Module 6: Email Management and Preservation" by InterPARES & ICA. July 2012. Available at : http://www.interpares.org/ip3/display_file.cfm?doc=ip3_canada_gs12_module_6_july-2012_DRAFT.pdf

Administrative or working emails and executive or decision-making emails should be retained according to their retention period. Contact the Archives team for further guidance on developing and using records retention schedules.

Best practices

Maintaining your mailbox

- Organize important messages into specific folders, by function or activity.
 - Right click on the sidebar and click on the “Create a new subfolder” option.
- Regularly delete unnecessary messages.
- Avoid using non-recommended messaging services (Gmail, Apple Mail, Yahoo Mail, etc.) for professional communication.
- Strictly separate professional emails from personal ones.
- Avoid using your mailbox as a long-term storage space.
- Apply retention periods consistently to emails based on their content and value.
 - Right click on a folder, select “Apply a strategy” and pick the appropriate retention period.

Receiving and classifying emails

- Recognize the binding nature of certain emails (decisions, approvals, validations).
 - For more information, see the decision tree.
- Treat professional emails as NGO-owned records when created or received in the context of work duties.
- If an email contains personal or sensitive data (e.g., HR or medical), classify it separately in a dedicated folder.
 - Right click on the sidebar and click on the “Create a new subfolder” option.
 - See the decision tree.
- Use naming conventions for saved emails and downloaded attachments.
 - See NGO’s internal naming convention.
- Only download attachments that are useful for your work.

Writing and sending emails

- Add a professional signature.
 - Go to Settings, then select “Account” and click on “Signatures”.
 - Avoid heavy images and long text.
- Only include in the “To” field the people directly responsible for acting.
 - Ask yourself, “who needs to act on this email?”
- Use “CC” only for those who should be informed, not to respond.
- Use BCC when sending mass emails to protect recipients’ privacy and avoid reply-all chains.
- Prefer links to shared documents instead of sending attachments.

Saving and transferring emails

- Export professional emails at the end of a function or activity and file them in the appropriate folder within the designated documents repository.
 - To determine what emails to save, see the decision tree.
- Before leaving your position, sort and clean your mailbox for transfer to ITSD.
 - Organize, delete non-relevant or sensitive content, and prepare a summary inventory.
 - To determine what emails to save, see the decision tree.
- Delete the original email from your inbox once saved elsewhere.
- Keep the original content of the message unchanged, including the subject line and body.
- Preserve all components of the email together, including attachments.

Main takeaways

- Treat professional emails as **records** when they are created or received in the context of work.
- Identify and preserve emails with **evidentiary** value.
- Use your professional email account **exclusively** for work-related communications.
- Classify separately emails with **personal or sensitive** information.
- Organize emails into **folders** by function or activity.
- Before leaving your position, **sort your mailbox** and transfer relevant messages to the appropriate repository.

Delete the email if it...

- Is purely personal, not related to professional activity
- Contains temporary information (event invites, outdated drafts, newsletters)
- Is a duplicate of a message already filed or archived
- Has no evidentiary value, and no action is required

Keep the email if it...

- Documents a decision, a validation, or an approval
- Contains a record of actions taken, instructions, or formal communications
- Is required to meet legal, administrative, or accountability obligations
- Involves strategic planning, meeting summaries, or policy development
- Relates to an ongoing matter requiring follow-up or reference
- Is part of a workflow, project, or activity and has long-term relevance

Questions?

If you have any questions or need further guidance, please contact the Archives team at: [email]